

Condensation of Ketones with Resorcinol. Part II.

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The condensation of one molecule of ketone with one molecule of resorcinol has been described in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 167). In the present investigation various ketones have been condensed with two molecules of resorcinol in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride and hydrochloric acid gas, the reaction taking place in the following manner.

A similar type of condensation was effected previously between benzil and four molecules of resorcinol by Liebig (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2332) and between anthraquinone and resorcinol (2 mols.) by Schawrin and Kusnezof (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2020) in presence of stannic chloride.

The most striking fact about the various condensation products described in this paper is that though they do not admit of quinonoid configuration according to the ordinary modes of tautomerisation, yet they are all coloured compounds producing more or less deeply coloured solutions with caustic alkali and also possessing dyeing properties in varying degrees. Thus they form an interesting group of non-quinonoid dyes, producing yellow, orange and brown shades on wool and silk, the brominated products producing beautiful red and bluish-red shades. Instances of non-quinonoid compounds (such as benzalnitroanilines, acenaphthylene, azobenzene, etc.) possessing colour, though rare, are not altogether unknown; but under no circumstances can they be regarded as true dyes.

By an extraordinary manipulation some sort of partially quinonoid structure may be given to some of the condensation products described in this paper after the analogy of the structure attributed to triphenylmethyl by Jacobson and others. Thus the anhydride of tetrahydroxytetraphenylmethane may be represented as having the following half-quinonoid structure,

but such an arrangement is altogether excluded in the case of the condensation products from fluorenone, camphor, *cyclohexanone* and antipyrine.

The condensation products with resorcinol are all more or less fluorescent in alkaline, alcoholic, and pyridine solutions, the alcoholic solution exhibiting the strongest fluorescence. The bromo-derivatives of the compounds possess much deep colour (red) and exhibit fluorescence in alcoholic and acetone solutions but not in alkaline solution.

The different condensation products obtained also afford an interesting study of the relation between colour and constitution. 4:4'-Dihydroxytetraphenylmethane (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1209) has been described as colourless, but the condensation product (I, R, R' = Ph) of benzophenone with resorcinol containing a pyrone ring in addition, possesses a dark brown colour, dissolves in alkali with deep orange colour and dyes wool and silk beautiful brownish-yellow shades. The replacement of one or two of the phenyl groups by methyl much weakens the tinctorial character as is shown by the condensation products derived from acetophenone and acetone, which dissolve in alkali solution with lighter colour and possess much feebler dyeing properties, the latter having very slight affinity for wool or silk.

The fluorescence of the three compounds however in alkaline or alcoholic solutions does not appreciably differ. But it is interesting to note that like the tinctorial character, the yields of the three compounds also vary with the number of the benzene nuclei, that of the benzophenone compound being greatest. It therefore appears that the reactivity of the CO-group under the conditions of the

present investigation increases with the increase in the negative character of the radicles in the ketone. It is also interesting to note that fluorenone reacts more rapidly than benzophenone, giving a better yield.

In the case of the condensation products of diketones like phenanthraquinone and benzil with resorcinol two series of compounds have been obtained, (a) the reaction taking place between one carbonyl group and two molecules of resorcinol, and (b) between two carbonyl groups and four molecules of resorcinol. It is interesting to note that the compounds of the second series exhibit much deeper colour and also stronger fluorescence, probably on account of their symmetrical structure.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method.—A mixture of the ketone (1 mol.) and resorcinol (2 mols.) was heated in a flask until they melted; powdered anhydrous zinc chloride was then added and dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into the flask. The temperature was gradually raised to 180-190° and heating continued for 3-5 hours. The product was thoroughly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution, filtered, and precipitated by dilute acetic or hydrochloric acid. The alkali-acid treatment was repeated several times. Finally it was crystallised from some organic solvent.

Condensation with Open-chain Monoketones.

Anhydride of Tetrahydroxytetraphenylmethane (I, R'=Ph) was prepared by heating benzophenone (3.6 g.) with resorcinol (4.4 g.) for 4-5 hours at 180°-190°. The crude product was washed successively with benzene, chloroform and ether and then dissolved in warm alcohol or acetone from which it separated as a brown microcrystalline powder melting at 125-127° (yield, 70%). It shows orange-green fluorescence in alkali and dyes wool and silk brownish-yellow. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 4.7. $C_{25}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 81.9; H, 4.9 per cent.).

Dipotassium Salt.—(Found: K, 17.6. $C_{25}H_{18}O_3$ requires K, 17.6 per cent.).

Dibromo-derivative.—Obtained by adding bromine to the alcoholic solution, it separated from absolute alcohol as a red microcrystalline powder, m.p. 175°. Alkaline solution does not fluoresce, while alcoholic solution fluoresces green. (Found: Br, 30.0, $C_{25}H_{16}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 30.5 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative crystallised from acetone; it is insoluble in benzene, ether, alcohol, and chloroform. (Found: C, 81.5; H, 4.5. $C_{30}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 81.5; H, 4.5 per cent.). Other products obtained by the condensation of resorcinol with open-chain monoketones are described in Table I.

Condensation with Cyclic Ketones.

Anhydride of Diphenyltetrahydroxydiphenylmethane.—Fluorenone (1.8 g.) and resorcinol (2.2 g.) were mixed with fused zinc chloride and heated in an atmosphere of hydrochloric acid gas for 8 hours. The product was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid; it was finally obtained from benzene as a bright yellow powder, m.p. 220° (yield, 85%). It is soluble in alcohol with a green fluorescence. It dyes wool and silk bright yellow. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 4.6. $C_{25}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 82.4; H, 4.4 per cent.).

Chloroacetyl Derivative.—Obtained by boiling with chloroacetyl chloride for 15-20 minutes, it formed colourless microcrystals, m.p. 182° from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform; it is easily soluble in chloroform but sparingly in alcohol. (Found: Cl, 13.5. $C_{29}H_{18}O_5Cl_2$ requires Cl, 13.7 per cent.). Other products of this series are described in Table II.

Condensation with Diketones.

Condensation Product of Benzil and Resorcinol (Formula I, R=Ph, R'=Bz).—Benzil (4 g.) and resorcinol (4 g.) were heated as usual for 3-4 hours. The product was finally washed with benzene, ether, chloroform and crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 215° (yield, 70%). It dyes wool red. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 4.7. $C_{28}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 79.1; H, 4.5 per cent.).

Dipotassium Salt.—(Found: K, 16.8. $C_{26}H_{16}O_4K_2$ requires K, 16.6 per cent.). Other products of this series are described in Table III.

TABLE I.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation (R = resorcinol).	M.p.	Analysis.		Properties.
				Calc.	Found.	
Anhydride of hepta-hydroxytetraphenylmethane.	I, R = Ph. R' = C ₆ H ₄ (OH);	R + trihydroxybenzophenone + fused ZnCl ₂ + dry HCl gas at 180° - 190° for 2 - 3 hours. Yield 80 - 85%.	No change up to 280°	C, 72.5 H, 4.3	72.8 4.4	Dark brown powder from alcohol.
Anhydride of tetrahydrotriphenylmethane.	I, R = CH ₃ , R' = Ph	R + acetophenone + ZnCl ₂ + HCl gas at 150° - 160° for 2 hrs. and at 180° - 190° for 3 hrs. Yield 50 - 60%.	152°	C, 78.9 H, 5.2	79.1 5.3	Orange powder from alcohol. Sparingly soluble in benzene, ether, chloroform, acetic acid. Alkali solution orange and fluorescent (green). Dyes wool light orange.
... Dibromo-derivative.	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄ Br ₂		160°	Br, 34.6	34.8	Microcrystals from absolute alcohol. Insoluble in ether, chloroform, benzene, soluble in acetone.
... Dibenzoyl derivative.	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ O ₂		115°	C, 79.6 H, 4.6	79.7 4.5	Purified from acetone. Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform and alcohol.

TABLE I—Contd.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation (R = resorcinol).	M.P.	Calc.	Analysis. Found.	Properties.
Anhydride of tetrahydroxydiphenyldimethylmethane.	I, R, R' = Me	R + acetone + ZnCl ₂ + dry HCl gas, at 50°–55° for 3 hrs. and at 180°–190° for 4 hrs. Yield 30–40%.	165°	C, 74.3 H, 5.8	74.5 6.06	Orange red powder (alcohol). Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, acetic acid. Soluble in acetone. Alkali solution light orange and fluorescent (green).
" Dibromo-derivative.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂		153°	Br, 40	40.1	Purified from absolute alcohol.

TABLE II.

Condensation product of resorcinol and camphor.	C ₉ H ₁₆ :C	R + camphor + ZnCl ₂ + HCl gas at 180°–190° for 7–8 hours.	200°	C, 78.5 H, 7.1	78.2 6.7	Obtained from alcohol as a dark red powder. Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, glacial acetic acid. Soluble in alcohol and acetone with green fluorescence. Dyes wool deep reddish-brown.
" Dipotassium salt.	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ K ₂			K, 18.9	19.0	

.. Dibenzoyl derivative.	$C_{36}H_{32}O_5$	120° C, 79.4 H, 5.8	79.4 5.8	Microcrystalline red powder (alcohol) from acetone. Insoluble in alcohol, ether, benzene, chloroform.
..	$C_{22}H_{22}O_3Br_2$	No change up to 280°.	32.4	Alkali solution deep red. Dyes wool bluish-red.
Dibromo-derivative.				
Anhydride of tetrahydroxydiphenylcyclohexane.	$ \begin{array}{c} C_6H_5.OH \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{Cyclohexane ring} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ C_6H_5.OH \end{array} $	Softens at 213° + ZnCl ₂ + HCl gas at 150° for 3 hrs. and at 180° for 3 hrs. - 190° composition. Yield 74%.	76.3 6.5	Reddish-brown powder (rectified spirit). Soluble in alcohol and acetone. Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, acetic acid. Alkali solution green fluorescent. Dyes wool and silk brownish-orange.
..	$C_{13}H_{10}O_3K_2$		21.9	Violet powder.
Dipotassium salt.				
..	$C_{18}H_{10}O_3Ba$	Adding BaCl ₂ solution to the potassium salt solution.	88	Brownish-orange microcrystalline powder.
Barium salt.				

TABLE II—Contd.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation. (R = resorcinol).	M.p.	Analysis. Calc. Found.	Properties.
Dibenzoyl-derivative.	$C_{12}H_{10}O_5$		Softens at 202°. 203°	C, 78.86 H, 5.31	Microcrystalline powder from benzene. Soluble in acetone, chloroform, pyridine. Insoluble in alcohol, ether.
"	$C_{18}H_{16}O_3Br_2$	By the action of Br in alcoholic solution.	No change up to 280°	Br, 86.98	Obtained from acetone as a red powder. Alkali solution red. Acetone solution red with green fluorescence. Insoluble in alcohol, ether, benzene, chloroform.
Condensation product of resorcinol and antipyrine.	$C_6H_3.OH$ $N_2H_{12}C_{11}$ $C_6H_3.OH$	R + antipyrine + $ZnCl_2$ + HCl gas at 180° - 190°, for 6 hrs. Yield 70%.	150°	N, 7.9	Obtained from alcohol as a dark brown powder. Alkali solution reddish-brown with green fluorescence. Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform. Dyes wool reddish-brown.
"	$C_{23}H_{18}O_3N_2Br_2$		190°	Br, 80.1	Obtained from alcohol and acetone as a red powder. Dyes wool deep red.
Dibromo-derivative.					

Anhydride of hexahydroxydiphenylcyclohexane.

.. Tetrapotassium salt, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6\text{K}_4$

.. Dibarium salt, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6\text{Ba}_2$

Condensation product of phenanthraquinone and Resorcinol (1 mol.).

*cyclo*Hexanone + pyrogallol + ZnCl_2 + HCl gas at $180^\circ - 160^\circ$, for about 8 hrs. Yield 80%.

No change up to 280°
 C, 68.79
 H, 5.73
 68.48
 5.92
 Black microcrystalline powder from alcohol; soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine; insoluble in benzene, ether, chloroform, petroleum ether. Dyes wool and silk a light yellow shade and iron-mordanted wool a brownish black shade.

K, 38.47 38.5 Grey powder.

Ba, 46.97 46.9

Adding BaCl_2 solution to the potassium salt solution.

TABLE III.

160°
 C, 79.58
 H, 4.08
 79.35
 4.28
 Soluble in alcohol and acetone with light blue fluorescence. Insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform.

Phenanthraquinone, (1 mol.) + R (2 mols.) + ZnCl_2 + HCl gas at $170^\circ - 180^\circ$. Yield 80%.

TABLE III—Contd.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation (R=resorcinol).	M.p.	Analysis. Calc.	Found.	Properties.
" Dibenzoyle de- rivative.	$C_{40}H_{34}O$		148°	C, 80.0 H, 4.0	79.9 4.1	Soluble in toluene, in- soluble in alcohol, ace- tone, ether, chloroform, benzene.
Condensation pro- duct of phenan- thraquinone (1 mol.) and resorci- nol (4 mols.).		The above dihy- droxy compound (1 mol.) + R (2 mols.) + $ZnCl_2$ + HCl gas at 190° - 185° for 5-6 hrs. After alkali and acid treat- ment, washed with ether, ben- zene, alcohol and acetone. Yield 60-70%.	No change up to 290°	C, 79.1 H, 4.1	79.1 4.1	Crystallised from pyridine. Alkali solution reddish- brown with green fluo- rescence. Dyes wool reddish-brown.
" Tetrabenzoyle derivative.	$C_{66}H_{40}O_{10}$		173°	C, 79.8 H, 4.0	79.8 4.1	Soluble in toluene.
" Tetra-potassium salt.	$C_{38}H_{20}O_6K_4$			K, 21.4	21.5	

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